

An Analysis of Directive Speech Acts In Anime “Oregairu” by Wataru Watari

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ABSTRAK

Penelitian ini bertujuan untuk menganalisis bentuk tindak tutur direktif dan fungsinya yang ada dalam anime Oregairu karya Wataru Watari. Oleh karena itu, penelitian ini diharapkan bermanfaat dalam mengilustrasikan fenomena direktif. Metode penelitian ini adalah penelitian kualitatif dan sumber data utama penelitian ini adalah naskah lengkap anime Oregairu karya Wataru Watari. Penelitian ini menggunakan teknik observasi dan dokumentasi dalam mengumpulkan data. Peneliti menganalisis data menggunakan teori Miles and Huberman's yaitu data collection, data reduction, data display dan conclusion. Penelitian ini memiliki dua tujuan. Tujuan pertama adalah mendeskripsikan bentuk tindak tutur direktif dalam dialog film anime Oregairu karya Wataru Watari. Tujuan kedua adalah mengetahui fungsi tindak tutur direktif dalam dialog Film Anime Oregairu karya Wataru Watari. Hasil penelitian ini terkait tindak tutur direktif dilihat dari aspek bentuk dan fungsi. Dalam dialog Anime Oregairu karya Wataru Watari ditemukan enam bentuk tindak tutur direktif, yaitu perintah, permintaan, ajakan, larangan, nasihat dan kritik. Dilihat dari fungsi tindak tutur direktif, dialog film Anime Oregairu

karya Wataru Watari memiliki berbagai fungsi. Bentuk tindak tutur direktif perintah memiliki fungsi memerintah, meminta, mengarahkan, memaksa dan mengharuskan. Bentuk tindak tutur direktif permintaan memiliki fungsi meminta, memohon, mengharap dan menawarkan. Bentuk tindak tutur direktif ajakan memiliki fungsi mengajak, mendorong, merayu dan menantang. Bentuk tindak tutur direktif larangan memiliki fungsi melarang dan mencegah. Bentuk tindak tutur direktif nasihat memiliki fungsi menyarankan, menghimbau dan mengingatkan. Bentuk tindak tutur direktif kritik memiliki fungsi mengkritik, menyindir, memaki dan marah.

ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the form of directive speech acts and their functions in the anime Oregairu by Wataru Watari. Therefore, this study is expected to be useful in illustrating the directive phenomenon. This research method is qualitative research and the main data source of this study is the complete script of the anime Oregairu by Wataru Watari. This study uses observation and documentation techniques in collecting data. The researcher analyzed the data using Miles and Huberman's theory, namely data collection, data reduction, data display and conclusion. This study has two objectives. The first objective is to describe the form of directive speech acts in the dialogue of the anime film Oregairu by Wataru Watari. The second objective is to determine the function of directive speech acts in the dialogue of the Anime Film Oregairu by Wataru Watari. The results of this study are related to directive speech acts seen from the aspects of form and function. In the dialogue of Anime Oregairu by Wataru Watari, six forms of directive speech acts are found, namely orders, requests, solicitation, prohibitions, advice and criticism. Judging from the function of directive speech acts, the dialogue of the Anime film Oregairu by Wataru Watari has various functions. The form of directive speech acts of commands has the functions of commanding, ordering, directing, forcing and requiring. The form of directive speech acts of requests has the functions of asking, begging, expecting and offering. The form of directive speech acts of invitations has the functions of inviting, pushing, seducing and challenging. The form of directive speech acts of prohibitions has the functions of prohibiting and preventing. The form of directive speech acts of advice has the functions of suggesting, appealing and reminding. The form of directive speech acts of criticism has the functions of criticism, satire, swearing and anger.

INTRODUCTION

The study of language is known as linguistics which includes phonology, morphology, syntax, semantics, and pragmatics. In this research, researchertook a pragmatic approach, namely the science that examines the relationship between symbols and their interpretation. Pragmatic theory which states that language must be used according to the context (Yule, 2020) so that a comprehensive understanding can be established. In conversation, a person expresses feelings through actions and behavior combined with speaking and listening.

In speech act activities, the speaker does not just convey a message but also builds a social relationship with the speech partner by expressing the speech appropriately, in other words the speaker does not just open his mouth when speaking, but often the speech partner may not always understand the speaker's intentions. Therefore, pragmatics is needed which examines the relationship between symbols and their interpretation by paying attention to context. The context in question is for example the circumstances, situation or environment in which communication occurs, including factors such as time, place, purpose, identity of the speaker and interlocutor, as well as cultural and social background. For example, when someone says "*sharp*" it can refer to physically sharp objects such as needles, knives and others or it can also be interpreted as someone's intelligence.

Speech acts are a study of the relationship between language and the context of how humans use language in social interactions. Austin (1962) in his book *how to do things with words*, states that basically when someone says something, he also does something. This statement then underlies the birth of speech act theory. (Yule, 2020) in speech acts are divided into three types, such as locutionary act, illocutionary act and perlocutionary act. These illocutionary utterances are further grouped by (Yule, 2020) into five parts, including: 1). Representatives speech acts 2). Directives speech acts 3). Commissive speech acts 4). Expressive speech acts 5). Declarations speech acts.

According to Yule (2006:92) a directive speech act is a type of speech act that expresses speech to a speech partner to order other people through the use of language that involves the speaker's efforts to influence the listener to do something (Syarif Husein, 2023). through the use of commands, requests, suggestions, or other instructions. Yule (2014) also states that speech acts have social and performative aspects. This means that when someone wants to use language to carry out a directive speech act, he does not just express an expression or meaning, but also carries out an action that causes a change in the listener's behavior as it is said so that the listener takes an action.

Researchers used the anime film *Oregairu* as a research object because one of the interesting and popular anime is *Oregairu* by *Wataru Watari*. This anime tells the story of Hachiman Hikagaya, a pessimistic, closed-minded and realistic teenager who is forced by his teacher to join a service club at his school and work with two girls who have their own problems. Directive speech acts are often expressed by characters in offering help and advice to others while dealing with the inner conflicts they experience.

In the context of the anime *Oregairu*, directive speech acts are often used by several characters in giving instructions to their team members, such as giving orders, requests, or suggestions. The ability to understand and use directive speech acts correctly is an important aspect of effective language learning. However, team members often have difficulty understanding and using directive speech acts appropriately. They may have difficulty identifying the meaning of statements or commands given by speakers. Therefore, research that focuses on analyzing the types and functions of directive speech acts in the anime *Oregairu* has significant relevance. By understanding in depth the directive speech acts used in context, the obstacles that team members may face can be identified and effective strategies can be found to improve the understanding and use of directive speech acts.

The following is an illustration of the directive speech acts that occur in the Anime *Oregairu* film in dialogue:

Context 1

Yukino : "*So... who is that confused guy?*"

Mrs. Shizuka : "*He wants to join (points to Hachiman)*"

Hachiman : "*I... (scratches head) class 2-F student Hikigaya Hachiman. Hmm... what are you joining?*"

The context of the dialogue above occurs in the volunteer club classroom when Mrs. Shizuka Hiratsuka orders Yukino to accept Hachiman to join the volunteer club with the intention of asking Yukino. In the conversation above, a directive speech act is found in the utterance "*He wants to join*" which is a directive speech act in the form of a command with a request function. Even though the utterance is vaguely declarative, according to the context, this utterance contains the intention of giving an order with the function of command. by Mrs. Shizuka is with the intention of giving an order to her speech partner to do what she said, namely giving an order to Yukino to accept Hachiman to join the volunteer club.

There are several studies similar to this research, including research conducted by Nydia Ramaniya (2022) on Directive and Expressive Speech Acts in the 1990 Novel *Dilan* by Pidi Baiq and their Implications for Indonesian Language Learning in High School. In her thesis, Nydia Ramaniya explains about directive and expressive speech acts in the novel *Dilan 1990* by Pidi Baiq and suggestions related to the results of this research. Nydia Ramaniya found that in the 1990 novel *Dilan* by Pidi Baiq, directive speech acts contain 6 communicative functions which are expressed directly or indirectly and expressive acts contain 6 communicative functions which tend to be expressed with direct speech acts. Meanwhile, in Reza Raditya (2019), entitled *Functions of Directive Illocutionary Acts in the Film Final Fantasy VII Advent Children*: explains the types and functions of directive illocutionary acts contained in the film as the object of his research. Reza Raditya discovered 5 types and functions of directive illocutionary acts, in which there are 31 command meanings which function to provide instructions to the speech partner to carry out an action. 12 meanings of request with the function of asking the speech partner to convey something. 18 meaning of invitation with the function of getting the partner involved in an action. 10 meanings of prohibitions whose function is not to allow the interlocutor to act or do something. 7 meaning of rejection with the function of not accepting an offer that aims to do something from the interlocutor.

Based on the previous research above, there are similarities and differences with this research. The similarity is that they both discuss directive speech acts. However, there are several differences including: 1). The research object that is used as a source of data acquisition. Nydia Ramaniya (2022) in her thesis uses novels as a source of data acquisition, while Reza Raditya (2019) uses films in his thesis as a source of data acquisition. This is different from the researchers in this study who used anime films as a source of data acquisition. 2). The difference in describing the main problem in Nydia Ramaniya's thesis (2022) is to describe the directive and expressive speech acts contained in the dialogue of the novel *Dilan 1990* by Pidi Baiq and describe the implications of research results and Indonesian language learning in high school. Furthermore, the difference in describing the main problem in Reza Raditya's thesis (2019) is, what types of directive illocutionary acts are found in the film *Final Fantasy VII Advent Children: Complete*. A more significant difference for researchers in this study is the types and functions of speech acts contained in the anime film *Oregairu* by *Wataru Watari*. 3). The next difference is the data analysis method used, in Nydia Ramaniya's thesis (2022) uses Heuristic analysis theory, while in Reza Raditya's thesis (2019) uses dialogue coding using the FFVIIACC/00.25:13/DP/01 method. The difference in the data analysis method used by researchers in this research is by using Miles & Huberman's theory.

Regarding the research background above, the researcher is interested in analyzing the types and functions of directive speech acts contained in the anime *Oregairu* by *Wataru Watari*. So the title of this research is *An Analysis of Directive Speech Acts in anime Oregairu by Wataru Watari*.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research has used qualitative methods where the data collected is in the form of words, utterances or text found in research sources. This research method uses descriptive-qualitative characteristics. The researcher employed an anime script analysis to explain the phenomenon of directive acts. Obtaining detailed information about the phenomenon of directive acts in anime scripts is the aim of descriptive study. In this research, data sources are divided into two types, namely primary and secondary data. The primary data source collected from the dialogue of the anime *Oregairu* by *Wataru Watari* which contains directive type speech acts.

In this research, data sources in the form of documentation, notes, articles, journals, theses or arguments relevant to the topic are secondary data that has been used in this research. Data collection techniques are a way for researchers to obtain data from sources on the object of this research which has been explained as follows:

1. Observation

The researcher has found the use of directive acts and the important things of directive acts in the anime script. Finally, the researcher has written the types of directive acts and their functions found in the anime.

2. Documentation

The document in question is secondary data obtained from the results of analysis of directive speech acts in the anime *Oregairu*. The researcher has gotten information and supporting references regarding directive acts from related electronic books and journals.

The data analysis technique that has been used in research according to Miles and Huberman (in Sugiyono, 2013) refers to an interactive model with the following steps:

1. Data Collection

To obtain data, researchers search for and collect data through observation and documentation. Researchers collected data in the form of directive speech acts contained in the anime *Oregairu* by

watching the anime online and then recording the dialogue included in the directive speech acts while always paying attention to the context.

2. Data Reduction

Reduction means summarizing, selecting and sorting. After the data was collected, the author selected the data to facilitate further analysis. Data reduction was carried out by classifying the utterances into six categories including Command, Request, Solicitation, Prohibitive, Advising and Criticism.

3. Data Display

The contents of all data must be able to be described by presentation. Descriptive narratives provide detailed and in-depth explanations in text form. However, tables can be used to help organize data systematically before explaining it in a narrative to make it easier to understand.

4. Conclusion

The final step in Miles and Huberman's theory is that the researcher has put forward initial conclusions that are supported by the data obtained, thus it can be said that there is a certain goal in data analysis. To show that the research objectives have been achieved, the researcher provides a concise and precise conclusion.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Form of Directive speech Act that occurs in the anime Film *Oregairu* by *Wataru Watari*

a. Directive Speech Act in the Form of a Command

Dialogue		Time	Episode
Yuighama	:	<i>"sorry, next time I will try"</i>	18:01-18:06
Hachiman	:	<i>"Teach her how to bake a cake properly"</i>	

The dialogue occurs in a cooking class where Yui asks the volunteer club members for help in learning how to bake a cake. In this conversation, the directive speech act found in the utterance *"Teach her how to bake a cake properly"* is a command. Hachiman's directive is intended to instruct the interlocutor (Yukino) to perform a specific action. (Prayitno, 2016) Command is an expression or behavior that conveys a commanding to the interlocutor to act according to what is stated. During the dialogue, Yui requests a help from the volunteer club members (Yukino and Hachiman) to assist her in baking a cake and to prove her cooking skills. However, Yui feels less confident due to frequent previous failures. Hachiman entrusts Yukino, who is confident and skilled, to teach Yui how to bake a cake. This indicates that the speech act aims to provide Yui with new understanding or to correct her understanding of baking a cake.

b. Directive Speech Act in the Form of a Request

Dialogue		Time	Episode
Saika	:	<i>"you are really great huh...Actually, could I ask you for a help?"</i>	07:15-07:22
Hachiman	:	<i>"ah... ask for help?"</i>	

The context of this dialogue takes place on the school grounds during sports time, while they are resting after playing tennis. Saika has noticed Hachiman's great tennis skills and is interested in inviting Hachiman to join their tennis club. In the conversation above, a directive speech act of request is found in the utterance *"Actually, could I ask you for a help?"* where Saika is asking Hachiman to consider joining the tennis club. (Yule, 2020) A request is when the speaker asks or implores their interlocutor to perform a certain action with a specific goal in mind. Saika's request aims for Hachiman to provide his assistance and join the tennis club, hoping to strengthen the club's performance or address issues related to the club.

c. Directive Speech Act in the Form of a Solicitation

Dialogue		Time	Episode
Yuighama	:	<i>"It's not poisonous! maybe you're right"</i>	16:32-16:44
Yukino	:	<i>"you don't want to die?Alright! Let's think of a way to make it better"</i>	

The context of this dialogue occurs after Yui has finished baking a cake, but the cake turned out poorly. Yukino, as the leader, has to address the issue and invites Yui and Hachiman to think of a better way to make the cake. The conversation above features a directive speech act of solicitation in the utterance

"Alright! Let's think of a way to make it better." An solicitation is a speech act used to direct or request someone to do something, intending for the interlocutor to follow along and participate in the action discussed by the speaker. In this utterance, it can be interpreted that Yukino is inviting Yui and Hachiman to collaborate or brainstorm together to help Yui improve her cake-making skills, given that Yui had previously failed. (Yule, 2020) An solicitation in the context of a directive speech act is an expression or utterance that aims to encourage or ask another person to do an action desired by the speaker. An solicitation is usually delivered in a more refined form than an order, and often uses more persuasive or polite language. This utterance is a type of directive solicitation as it encourages the interlocutors to engage in the process of thinking together.

d. Directive Speech Act in the Form of a Prohibition

Dialogue		Time	Episode
Yuighama	:	19:57-20:21	1
Yukino	:		

The context of the dialogue above occurs in the volunteer club classroom when Hachiman forbids Yui from calling him Hikki. In the conversation above, a type of directive speech act is found in the utterance *"Don't call me Hikki"* which is a form of directive speech act in the form of a prohibition. The type of prohibition carried out by Hachiman is with the intention of prohibiting the speech partner (Yui) from doing something. (Yule, 2020) A prohibition in the context of a directive speech act is an expression or utterance that aims to prevent or stop someone from carrying out an action. So, a prohibition directive is an action or statement that is intended for the speech partner not to do something according to the utterance.

e. Directive Speech Act in the Form of Advice

Dialogue		Time	Episode
Hachiman	:	08:04-08:24	3
Yukino	:		

The context of the dialogue above occurs in the volunteer club classroom when Yukino advises Hachiman to find a better solution. In the conversation above, the type of directive speech act is found in the utterance *"that way they won't develop, that's not the right solution"* which is a form of directive speech act in the form of advice. The type of advice given by Yukino is intended to provide advice to rethink what the speech partner (Hachiman) is doing to do something. (Yule, 2020) Advice in directive speech acts is speech that is intended to provide suggestions or guidance to the listener regarding what actions should be taken. Advice is usually given with the aim of helping the listener make better decisions or avoid mistakes. Directive Advice is an action or statement that is intended to provide good speech to the speech partner in doing something according to the speech.

f. Directive Speech Act in the Form of Criticism

Dialogue		Time	Episode
Yukino	:	19:33-19:46	2
Zaimokuza	:		

The context of the dialogue above occurs in the volunteer club classroom when Yukino criticizes Zaimokuza's writing. In the conversation above, a directive speech act is found in the utterance *"Maybe you should improve your common sense before writing."* which is a form of directive speech act in the form of criticism. The type of criticism carried out by Yukino is intended to criticize Zaimokuza's writing in order to improve rational and wise thinking in writing something. (Yule, 2020) Directive Criticism is a form of directive speech act in which the speaker attempts to direct or influence the listener through criticism. Criticism in this context usually contains a negative assessment of someone's actions, behavior, or ideas, with the hope that the listener will improve or change something. Criticism in directive speech

acts is speech that aims to point out someone's shortcomings or mistakes in the hope that they will take corrective action. Directive criticism is an action or statement that is intended to provide harsh speech to the interlocutor.

The study of directive speech acts in Wataru Watari's anime *Oregairu* can provide several implications:

1. Deeper Understanding of Characters and Relationships Between Characters

By analyzing directive speech acts, viewers or readers can better understand the dynamics of relationships between characters in *Oregairu*. For example, how the main characters use language to influence the actions of others can reflect their personalities, the power they have, or the social relationships between them.

2. Implications to Pragmatic Linguistic Studies

This research can add to the literature on speech acts in the context of Japanese culture, especially in popular media such as anime. It can help broaden the understanding of how directives are used in modern Japanese, as well as the role of cultural context in shaping language use.

3. Implications for language learning Language

This research is useful for English language learning because it helps students understand the use of language in social contexts (pragmatics), develop speaking and listening skills, and enrich cross-cultural understanding through a comparison between communication methods. This study can be used as a reference in teaching Japanese, especially in teaching pragmatics and speech acts to language learners. Teachers can use examples from *Oregairu* to show how directives are used in everyday contexts in Japan, thereby helping students understand the nuances of language use in different social situations.

4. Influence on Writing and Character Development in Popular Media

This research can also provide guidance for screenwriters or other content creators in creating realistic and in-depth dialogues, especially in depicting social interactions and conflicts between characters. Overall, the implications of this research can be very broad, depending on the perspective taken and how the results of this research are applied in various fields.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the presentation in the analysis of chapter 4, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. The form of directive speech acts in the anime dialogue *Oregairu* by Wataru Watari is divided into six, namely command, requests, solication, prohibitions, advice and Criticism. The results of the data analysis are 85 there are 23 utterances that find of command, 26 utterances of request, 12 utterances of solication, 7 utterances of prohibitive, 6 utterances of advising and 11 utterances of criticism.
2. The function of directive speech acts in the anime *Oregairu* by Wataru Watari has various functions such as form of command with commanding function totaling 11 utterance, ordering function totaling 3 utterance, directing function totaling 5 utterance, forcing function totaling 2 utterance and requiring function totaling 2 utterance. In the form of request directive with asking function totaling 6 utterance, begging function totaling 11 utterance, expecting function totaling 7 utterance and offering function totaling 2 utterance. In the form of solication directive with inviting function totaling 6 utterance, pushing function totaling 1 utterance and seducing function totaling 1 utterance. Prohibitive directive form with prohibiting function totaling 3 utterance and preventing function totaling 4 utterance. Advising directive form with suggesting function totaling 4 utterance, appealing function totaling 1 utterance, reminding function totaling 1 utterance. The form of the criticism directive with the criticism function totaling 2 utterance, the satire function totaling 1 utterance, the swearing function totaling 6 utterance and the anger function totaling 2 utterance by adjusting the context contained in the speech act in the anime *Oregairu* by Wataru Watari.

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